

Popular Article

Nutritional Management of Gastric Disease in Dogs

Manish Arya¹, Pradeep Chandra², Shashikant Gupta², Sangram Dash² and Dhaval Kamothi³

¹Ph.D. Scholar, Division of Veterinary Surgery and Radiology, ICAR-Indian Veterinary Research Institute, Izatnagar, U.P., 243122

²Ph.D. Scholar, Division of Animal Reproduction, ICAR-Indian Veterinary Research Institute, Izatnagar, U.P., 243122

³Ph.D. Scholar, Division of Veterinary Pharmacology & Toxicology, ICAR-Indian Veterinary Research Institute, Izatnagar, U.P., 243122

Abstract

The gastrointestinal (GI) tract is a complex tubular system primarily responsible for assimilation, digestion, absorption of nutrients and water from food and expelling wastes from the body in the form of faeces. Gastrointestinal diseases are one of the problems encountered in clinical practice. There are various treatment regimens for treating gastric diseases. Nutritional management may provide an alternate choice for management of gastric diseases by maintaining immunity and restoration of normal microflora in gut epithelium. However, some food components can trigger allergic and anaphylactic reactions in dogs. Thus, proper formulation of balanced diet is necessary for treating dogs suffering from impaired digestive system.

Introduction

A healthy gastrointestinal tract and a balanced diet are essential for the performance of various functions, such as protection against pathogens by maintaining the commensal microflora. Balanced diet helps in maintaining a normal gastrointestinal tract by promoting the growth of commensal microflora and repairing damaged epithelium. Various nutritional characteristics such as composition and consistency of food, frequency of feeding, etc. can affect gastric recovery and treatment of gastric diseases.

Most common signs associated with digestive disorders include vomiting, diarrhoea, anorexia and weight loss. Depending upon severity and location of disease, medical management and sometimes surgical management is routinely performed for restoring normal functions. Nutritional management can act as help as better alternative by promoting stimulus to the release of digestive hormones and entero-hormones, maintenance of the gut-associated lymphoid tissue (GALT) and by increasing mesenteric blood flow for replication and differentiation of intestinal cells, IgA secretion, and others. However, dietary factors can produce severe side effects, such as systemic inflammatory response, osmotic diarrhoea, and shortened gastrointestinal transit time.

Carbohydrate (CHO) is one of the easily digestible components in diet which helps in providing immediate source of energy. However, canine diet doesn't require CHO as it is generally of plant origin such as starch, white rice etc. and complexity. However, it may contain gluten such as in wheat, oats, and barley and may cause allergic reaction to some dog breeds such as Irish setters and soft coated Wheaten terriers. Similarly, dietary fibers are a large, complex group of CHO including starch and non-starch polysaccharides which is readily digested by bacterial enzymes as comparison to mammalian digestive enzymes.

Proteins in diet help in increasing lower esophageal sphincter pressure, which provides a great stimulus for secretion of GI hormones, including gastrin and pancreatic hormones, increasing gastric emptying and intestinal transit. However, dietary proteins can act as potent antigens by crossing gastric mucosal barrier in case of severe mucosal disruption (eg, inflammatory bowel disease [IBD], lymphoma), and act as antigen to the immune cells of the lamina propria resulting in hypersensitive reactions such as vomiting, diarrhea, weight loss, pruritus, hair loss, or otitis externa etc.

Dietary fat enhances the palatability and acceptance of food. It helps in promoting cellular growth and repair by providing phospholipids and cholesterol as building blocks. Meat, milk and egg act as major source of these nutrients in diet. Similarly, dietary fat can reduce tone of esophageal sphincter thus increasing risk of gastrointestinal leaking or vomiting. Due to complex digestion and assimilation, fat deposition is common in gastric diseases. However, complete absence of fat in diet may lead to deficiency of essential fatty acids. Dietary fat act as essential energy source in dogs suffering from gastric diseases due to their inability to digest CHO during periods of stressed starvation.

An ideal gastritis diet should be highly digestible, high in protein and CHO, lower in fat than the regular diet, hypoallergenic (having minimal or fewer allergens), and generous amounts of electrolytes (e.g., potassium, magnesium) and vitamins (both water soluble). and fat soluble) for performing normal functions in body. Sometimes in the early stages of therapy, a sacrificial diet (diet high in dietary fat) is given until the inflammation of GI disease is controlled. Various authors recommend feeding dogs with acute gastritis small amounts of bland food (diet free of coarse and spicy food) including fasting, followed by feeding three to four times a day. Fasting is a traditional treatment used in dogs to ensure bowel sparing during acute onset. However, in case of acute gastroenteritis in humans, provision of small amounts of bland food often reduces nausea and improves diarrhea. Therefore, total restriction of food intake for a short period may be beneficial, but early return to an appropriate oral regimen is strongly recommended unless the problem requires nothing per os to prevent further aggravation of the disease (e.g., pancreatitis).

There is very little information on the best diet for canine ulcerative or inflammatory gastric

disease. In general, frequent small meals, a more fluid diet, and a reduction in dietary fat content have been recommended to minimize gastric acid secretion and accelerate gastric emptying. Now a days, there is greater commercial availability of highly digestible diets feed with slightly different protein and CHO sources, different fat levels, and the presence or absence of other added nutraceuticals such as FOS or omega-3 fatty acids. Although high-fat meals decrease gastric emptying, lipids in foods such as cottage cheese provide an intragastric lipid emulsion that improves the hydrophobicity of the gastric mucosal barrier. In general, the commercially available highly digestible canned foods are acceptable for most pets with gastritis or peptic ulcer disease because they have modest amounts of protein, low fat levels, and are more easily emptied from the stomach than dry foods. It is important to remember that liquid CHO-based diets have a very rapid rate of emptying from the stomach and therefore can cause bloating. Milk, earlier was removed from diet as it may lead to stimulation of gastric acid secretion by the calcium and protein in milk. However, due to ability of lipid emulsions present in milk for improving the hydrophobicity of the gastric mucosal barrier has given a new interest in milk feeding.

Conclusion

Frequent small meals have shown symptomatic relief of clinical signs due to minimal gastric distension, but no effect on mucosal healing. A liquid diet may increase the likelihood of bloating due to increased gastric emptying, while minimizing protein content may decrease gastric acid secretion. High-fibre diets have traditionally been considered contraindicated in gastric disorders because of abrasive action on mucosa. However, the buffering effect of insoluble fibre and its acceleration of gastric emptying may one day prove valuable. Conversely, in gastric dumping syndromes, the addition of gel-forming fibre that slows gastric emptying (e.g., 3% w/v psyllium) may prove beneficial. Nutritional management of delayed gastric emptying has limited efficacy. Vagotomy accelerates voiding of liquids but decreases voiding of solids, implying that voiding disorders resulting from neuropathies (such as dysautonomia or diabetic neuropathy) may be improved by feeding liquid diets. Emptying is delayed with the use of hyperosmolar and high-fat foods. Therefore, liquid foods should be isosmolar diluted and contain little fat in the first few days of therapy. Unfortunately, such foods often have insufficient energy density to sustain animals for long periods of time.

References

- Burkholder, W.J., 1995. Metabolic rates and nutrient requirements of sick dogs and cats. *Journal of the American Veterinary Medical Association*, 206(5), pp.614-618.
- Davenport, D.J., Remillard, R.L., Simpson, K.W. and Pidgeon, G.L., 2000. Gastrointestinal and exocrine pancreatic disease. *Small Animal Clinical Nutrition*, ed, 4, pp.725-810.
- Eastwood, M.A., 1992. The physiological effect of dietary fiber: an update. *Annual review of nutrition*, 12(1), pp.19-35.

- Guilford, W.G., 1997. Effect of diet on inflammatory bowel diseases. *Veterinary Clinical Nutrition*, 4, pp.58-62.
- Klein, S., 1990. Glutamine: an essential nonessential amino acid for the gut. *Gastroenterology*, 99(1), pp.279-281.
- Lichtenberger, L.M., 1993. Mechanisms of gastric mucosal protection. In *Proc Am Coll Vet Int Med Forum* (Vol. 11, pp. 74-76).
- Mueller, R. and Tsohalis, J., 1998. Evaluation of serum allergen-specific IgE for the diagnosis of food adverse reactions in the dog. *Veterinary Dermatology (United Kingdom)*.
- Pemberton, C.M., Moxness, K.E., German, M.J., Nelson, J.K. and Gastineau, C.F., 1988. *Mayo Clinic diet manual: a handbook of dietary practices* (No. Ed. 6). BC Decker, Inc..
- Reppas, C., Meyer, J.H., Sirois, P.J. and Dressman, J.B., 1991. Effect of hydroxypropylmethylcellulose on gastrointestinal transit and luminal viscosity in dogs. *Gastroenterology*, 100(5), pp.1217-1223.
- Russell, J. and Bass, P., 1985. Canine gastric emptying of fiber meals: influence of meal viscosity and antroduodenal motility. *American Journal of Physiology-Gastrointestinal and Liver Physiology*, 249(6), pp.G662-G667.